

GraspOS Infrastructure - User Manual

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1) Introduction

The GraspOS infrastructure¹ is an ecosystem that consists of (a) a set of open, federated resources, including data, tools, services, templates, and guidelines, which support research assessment processes with an emphasis on those enabling Open Science-aware Responsible Research Assessment (OS-aware RRA), and (b) an open meta-catalogue that collects these resources improving their interoperability and discoverability, effectively catalysing the creation of an open, federated research assessment dataspace.

The GraspOS infrastructure was designed and developed in the context of the GraspOS Horizon Europe project². The aim was to be open and accessible, enabling the research community to contribute to its development and use. The infrastructure is based on a federated architecture and is distributed across multiple locations to be more resilient and adaptable to changing needs and contexts. It consists of core catalogues and registries that facilitate the discovery of research assessment resources, a Data Interoperability & Access Layer (DIAL) that enhances the interoperability of federated data sources, and a web-based front-end that serves as the entry point to the infrastructure. Additionally, the catalogues are designed to integrate seamlessly with the EOSC ecosystem. Figure 1 summarises the high-level architecture and more details can be found in GraspOS deliverables D4.2³ and D4.5⁴.

Figure 1: Overview of the GraspOS infrastructure core components

¹ <https://graspos-infra.athenarc.gr/catalogue/>

² <https://graspos.eu/>

³ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13618530>

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.17339531> (to be available from Nov 2025)

This document serves as a user guide focusing on the functionalities of the GraspOS infrastructure front-end user interface. For simplicity, from this point onward, we will refer to this interface simply as the GraspOS infrastructure.

If you need any clarification regarding this guide, require support, or have suggestions for improvements, please don't hesitate to contact us at graspos-pm@athenarc.gr.

2) Basic user functions

2.1) User login

Although all resource records in the GraspOS infrastructure are publicly visible without requiring users to log in, certain parts of the user interface are restricted to registered users. These restricted sections allow users to register new resources or edit existing resource details. Anyone wishing to perform these actions must first create an account and sign in to the GraspOS infrastructure.

An already registered user can log in to the infrastructure by clicking on the “LOGIN” button located at the top-right corner of the user interface. This action will open a pop-up window (Figure 2) where the user will provide their own credentials to login.

Figure 2: Login form of the GraspOS infrastructure

After connecting, the user is redirected to the main page of the interface. At the top-right corner, a user icon is displayed that can be clicked to provide user options (e.g., view basic profile information, add resource).

2.2) User registration

Any user who wishes to register with the GraspOS infrastructure (e.g., to add new resources) should first click the “LOGIN” button located in the top-right corner of the user interface. Then, in the pop-up window that appears (see Figure 2), they should follow the link to the registration form. The form will open as a new pop-up (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Registration form of the GraspOS infrastructure

The user should provide a unique and properly formatted username, a password, a valid email address, and correctly complete a captcha challenge. Optionally, they could also provide their full name, ORCID, and the affiliation through which they are affiliated. After completing the fields, the user can click on the “REGISTER” button to complete the registration. An automatic email will be sent to the user so that the registered email address will be confirmed. After clicking on the link in this email, the respective registered user will be created and the user can follow the instructions to login (see Section 2.1).

2.3) User details modification & password reset

A registered user can update certain details provided during the registration process (Section 2.2). Specifically, all fields except for the username and the verified email address can be modified. To do this, the user should click the user options button located in the top-right corner of the interface and select “Profile.” A pop-up window will then appear, allowing the user to edit

the relevant metadata fields (Figure 4). After making the desired changes, the user must click “SAVE” to apply the updates to the user database. There is also an option within this window to initiate a password reset by selecting the corresponding option.

The screenshot shows a 'My profile' window with a dark blue header and a white body. The header contains the text 'My profile' and a close button (X). The body contains several input fields with labels and current values: 'Username*' with 'vergoulis_cat', 'Email*' with 'vergoulis@duck.com', 'First Name' with 'Thanasis', 'Last Name' with 'Vergoulis', 'Orcid' (empty), and 'Organization' (empty). At the bottom, there are two buttons: 'RESET PASSWORD' and 'SAVE' with a save icon.

Figure 4: Form to edit user details

3) Resource management

3.1) Resource registration

Any registered user can add a new resource to the GraspOS infrastructure. The process involves filling in the resource metadata according to the latest version of the GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema⁵. This is a two-step process:

1. The user first creates a basic catalogue entry for the resource (for Data⁶, Tools⁷, and Templates / Guidelines⁸, the catalogue is based on a Zenodo community; for Services⁹, the catalogue is based on a deployment of the OpenAIRE Service Catalogue).
2. Then, the user registers the respective catalogue entry into the GraspOS infrastructure user interface and enriches the entry with additional metadata according to the GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema.

Once the metadata is submitted, the resource does not become publicly available immediately. Instead, a notification is sent to a GraspOS moderator, who reviews the submission to ensure it meets the basic requirements of the GraspOS inclusion policy (e.g., related to the completeness and quality of the metadata, the relevance of the resource to the scope of the infrastructure). After the moderator approval, the respective resource becomes published in the GraspOS infrastructure.

To add a resource, the user needs to first click on the user icon, that is located at the top-right corner of the user interface, to display the user menu (Figure 5). Then, the user should click on the “Add resource” option.

Figure 5: Snapshot from the user icon and menu.

This action opens a pop-up window (Figure 6), where the user is prompted to provide the corresponding Zenodo DOI/URL (for Data, Tools, and Templates/Guidelines) or the GraspOS Service Catalogue URL (for Services).

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17240298>

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos-datasets>

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos-tools>

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos-assessment-process-resources>

⁹ <https://graspos-services.athenarc.gr/>

Figure 6: Pop-up to initiate resource registration based on existing catalogue entry.

After entering a valid DOI/URL, the user is redirected to a resource registration form (Figure 7). In this form, any metadata that can be retrieved from the relevant catalogue is automatically pre-filled.

Figure 7: Main resource registration form.

It should be noted that if any required fields are missing from the corresponding Zenodo or OpenAIRE catalogue entry, an error message will inform the user about the missing metadata. In such cases, the user must update the relevant Zenodo or OpenAIRE entry to include the missing information. Access to the resource registration form will not be granted until all required fields are properly completed.

In the resource registration form (Figure 7), the user can add or edit additional metadata (compliant with the GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema) that can improve the discoverability of the resource. In case all required fields have been completed, the “ADD+” button that exists at the bottom-right corner of the pop up will be enabled and can be used by the user to complete the resource registration. It should be noted that those fields that are automatically harvested from the respective core catalogue, are only displayed and cannot be modified from this form (see also Section 3.3).

More details about the semantics of each metadata field and the expected values can be found in the GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema definition document (linked in the beginning of this section).

3.2) Resource editing & deletion

Each user has the ability to edit or delete any entry they have created. To do so, they can click the options icon (three vertical dots) located in the top-right corner of the entry and select either Edit or Remove from the menu (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Menu to select a resource for editing or deletion.

When editing an entry, a form similar to the resource registration form (Section 3.1) appears in a pop-up window, allowing the user to modify any metadata field of the resource. It should be noted that only fields that are not harvested by the respective core catalogue can be modified through this form (see also Section 3.3).

When deleting an entry, a warning message is displayed in a pop-up window, asking the user to confirm that the action is intentional. If the user confirms, the entry is permanently deleted.

3.3) Synchronisation with core catalogues

As mentioned in Section 3.1, each record in the GraspOS infrastructure requires a basic catalogue entry for the corresponding resource. To prevent inconsistencies and avoid redundant data entry by end users, metadata originating from the respective core catalogue (e.g., the Data catalogue¹⁰, which is implemented as a Zenodo community) cannot be edited directly within the GraspOS platform. If any changes are needed in these fields, they must be made in the core catalogue itself (e.g., in Zenodo). Once updates are made there, they are automatically synchronized with the GraspOS infrastructure, ensuring that the information remains up to date. As a result, end users are not responsible for manually synchronizing resource metadata.

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos-datasets>

4) Search interface

A snapshot of the main search interface of the GraspOS infrastructure is illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9: The main search interface of the GraspOS infrastructure with key sections highlighted

There are four key sections in this user interface:

- **Keyword Search Section (blue box):** Contains the search box where users can enter keywords to retrieve relevant resources.
- **Search Results Section (green box):** Displays a list of resources that match the user-provided keywords and meet the criteria defined through the Exploration Paths and Additional Search Options.
- **Exploration Paths Section (magenta box):** Provides various useful facets that help users refine the specific characteristics of the resources they want to discover.
- **Additional Search Options Section (orange box):** Offers extra filters and sorting options to further narrow down the search results, ensuring they are tailored to the user's needs.

It should be noted that the various facets and filters rely on specific metadata fields, hence more details related to their semantics can be found in the GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema¹¹. Additionally, it is worth mentioning that each record in the search results section is represented by a compact item that summarises the most important metadata fields. To display all metadata

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17240298>

fields of a particular resource of interest, the user needs to be redirected to the resource details page by clicking on the title hyperlink of the resource.

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